

Outcome of the European Maritime Day Workshop: Algae Solutions for a Thriving Blue Economy

Organised by

Algae cultivation produces measurable environmental value while supporting new bio-based products and industrial applications

Why has scaling not occurred despite technological progress and policy ambition?

The European ambition is clear: through the Ocean Pact and other EU initiatives the Commission aims to boost the competitiveness of the blue bioeconomy and support prioritisation of aquatic biomass. More than 650 million euro has already gone into developing the algae sector in the past years through 250+ research and innovation grants. The technology and methodologies for cultivation and refinery processes are now mature to scale, and there is data available to support implementation of ecosystem service valorisation. New products with high market potential are ready to support resilient food and feed production, reduce the use of chemical fertiliser and enhance health of soils and waters. Skilled workers from both industry and academia can offer important societal impact benefiting the rural, coastal areas. Yet, the public investment is at risk of being wasted due to regulatory barriers and systemic failure in the process of scaling. To fulfil the European Commission ambition, we urgently need policy innovation allowing algae to take the place it deserves.

The Horizon Europe funded projects SEAMARK, REALM and CIRCALGAE (2022-2026) aimed to innovate cultivation of macroalgae and microalgae, at open sea and in IMTA¹ settings on land, and to utilise industrial side-streams from traditional algal extraction businesses. The three projects together represent 61 partners across 18 countries from industry, research, and non-profit organisations. The projects cross cutting needs are accelerating biorefinery circularity, valuing algal ecosystem services and navigating algal scale-up costs. The most actionable solutions identified revolve around enabling and diversifying sales and products in the EU, and providing algal value streams the opportunity to fairly compete with other products as well as non-EU countries.

¹ *Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture*

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Action points:

- Enable sales in EU with fast product registration and certification alignment including new feedstocks like cultivated micro- and macroalgae.
- Reducing unfair competition between EU and non-EU companies through substitutes, accelerated customer validation and offtake partnerships.
- Develop financing mechanisms recognising ecosystem value to support transition from pilot systems to industrial coordination.
- Innovate legislative barriers to enable deployment of algae facilities in agriculture land and allow biomass cultivation in wastewater streams complying with European safety standards.
- Other important actions identified revolved around reducing production costs and finding pathways to allow for valorisation of ecosystem services or sustainability provisions from algae cultivation.

The EMD Workshop reinforced one very clear message:

“The European algae sector has not failed to scale. But the system has not yet adapted to value it.”

The three projects stress that funding alone is not enough for successful implementation of the project results, and the need for systematic change in the context of the European algae sector policy action is key to speeds up the industry scaling.

With regards,

Additional reading:

- CIRCALAE deliverables ([Zenodo repository](#)): *D1.1. Report of the current algae industry in Europe. D3.1. Report of the Definition of Requirements and Specifications for Final Products. D5.1. Report of the algae derived product market in Europe. D6.3. Policy Brief and recommendations on sustainable algae biorefinery. D4.1. European regulatory compendium for new algae product.*
- SeaMark deliverables ([Zenodo repository/homepage](#)): *D9.6: Policy and investor recommendation on the inclusion of business cases and monitorization of ecosystem services in policies. D10.3: Assessment of the EU regulatory landscape in a global content. D10.8: Policy and Investor Recommendation. D10.10: Strategic development plan for the Scale-up of the European seaweed industry D11.4: Report on clustering activities.*
- REALM's deliverable D7.4 on “Policy brief on the regulatory framework for water discharge and reuse” can be found in <https://realmalgae.eu/resources/>; new material will be published in the coming months.

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